

Mature Journal of the International Institute of Christian Theologians, Scholars, and Professionals. E-ISSN: 3027-1525 <https://mature.ictsp.org/>

TYPES OF BIBLICAL RESEARCH DESIGNS: A GUIDE TO BIBLICAL RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Dele Alaba ILESANMI, PhD^{1,2,3}

¹Lecturer, Redeemed Christian Bible College

²Global Director of Research and Development, International Institute of Christian Theologians, Scholars, and Professionals

³Associate Research Professor of Biblical Christian Education and Biblical Research, Testament Theological Seminary

pstdeleilesanmi3@gmail.com +234-08062197040

Abstract

Research, particularly biblical research, should be of interest not only to the academics but to professionals, church leaders, ministers and workers, theological institutions, and anyone who seeks true knowledge and wants to keep his/her knowledge fresh and up-to-date. Biblical Research is a purposeful, systematic, and spiritual epistemological inquiry into the truth to uncover the *revealed hidden truth* of God's word as recorded in Scripture to establish and advance true wisdom, knowledge and understanding. Many people do not know that research is a divine directive. Hence, this paper aims to present new and interesting thoughts in research into the concern of Christian researchers and academics from a biblical frame of reference. To achieve this aim, the study discusses types of biblical designs and biblical research types embellished with copious biblical examples as a guide and framework to biblical research methodology.

Keywords: biblical research, research, types of biblical research design, biblical research types, biblical research methodology.

Introduction

Research in any field of study could be seen as a dreary and difficult exercise if the researcher is not given a proper orientation. According to A.K. Omoyola (1990), “Researching becomes difficult, burdensome and uninteresting where individual feels that the challenges of research are not worth any effort”¹. Research, particularly biblical research, should be of interest not only to the academics but to professionals, church leaders, ministers and workers, theological institutions, and anyone who seeks true knowledge and wants to keep his/her knowledge fresh and up-to-date. Many people do not know that research is a divine directive. Hence, this paper is set to present new and interesting thoughts in research into the concern of Christian researchers and academics from biblical frame of reference. It discusses types of biblical designs and biblical research types as guides to biblical research methodology. It aims to obtain new finding and validate existing biblical data about research, research types, and types of research design embellished with copious examples. Hence the author employs a biblical descriptive-innovative approach² to understanding and applying God’s word through research.

Definition of Term

The word research has been defined in many ways. It can be seen as a “careful, systematic and objective investigation conducted to obtain valid facts, draw conclusions and established principles regarding an identifiable problem in some field of knowledge”³. Research can also be defined as “the manner with which we solve knotty problems in our attempt to push back the frontiers of human ignorance”⁴. The recent works by Dele Alaba Ilesanmi titled, “*Biblical research: A theological and epistemological inquiry*” and “*The Need for Biblical Research and Publication Beyond Secularism: Concepts and Importance*”, give a vivid and comprehensive understanding of the word “research”.

On the other hands, Ilesanmi defined Biblical Research as “a truth-seeking spiritual activity to uncover or discover the revealed hidden truth of God’s Word”. He goes further to give a broad definition of biblical research as “a purposeful, systematic, and spiritual epistemological inquiry into the truth to uncover the *revealed hidden truth* of God’s word as recorded in Scripture to establish and advance true wisdom, knowledge and understanding”⁵.

¹ Omoyola, A.K. “Need for research and basic research designs in education and social sciences” in Olu-Aderounmu, W.O and Bandele, S.O (eds.). *Methods of educational research: A book of readings*, (Kola Okanlawon Publishers Ltd, 1990) pp. 8-17.

² A “biblical descriptive-innovative research” is a type of biblical research design that provides a comprehensive overview of a subject or phenomenon by describing "what" exists in the Bible to bring about new ideas or thoughts to what is already known in research with the aim to providing deeper understanding and better application to God’s word. The name is coined by this author.

³ Ilesanmi cited Clarke and Clarke in Ilesanmi, Dele Alaba. “Biblical research: A theological and epistemological inquiry” in *Mature journal of the institute of Christian theologians, scholars, and professionals*, Vol. 2(2), 2024.

⁴ Ilesanmi, Dele A. “The Need for Biblical Research and Publication Beyond Secularism: Concepts and Importance” in *Mature journal of the institute of Christian theologians, scholars, and professionals*, Vol. 2(3), 2024.

⁵ Op. cit. Ilesanmi, Dele Alaba. “Biblical research: A theological and epistemological inquiry, 2024. Read the following biblical data about research (Deut 4:29; Job 11:7; Ps 119: 160;

Biblical Research Design and Types

What is Research Design?

Research design refers to the overall plan or framework that guides the process of conducting a research study. It encompasses the strategic method used to collect, analyse, and interpret data systematically. It serves as a roadmap for the research project, ensuring that the study is conducted in a logical, systematic, and rigorous manner. In essence, research design is the foundation of a research project, guiding the entire research process to produce meaningful and credible results. Generally, research design serves as a blueprint for the study, ensuring that it is methodologically sound and that the results are valid and reliable. Though not all, a good research design should include:

1. Clearly define the research question and objectives
2. Identify the research methodology and methods
3. Describe the sampling strategy and population
4. Outline the data collection and analysis procedures
5. Ensure validity, reliability, and generalizability
6. Address potential biases and limitations
7. Provide a timeline and budget plan

Research design types include:

1. Experimental design
2. Quasi-experimental design
3. Survey design
4. Case study design

Prov 23:23; 25:2; Eccl 7:25; Isa 34:16; Jer 29:13; Hos 10:12; Matt 7:7-8; Lk 11:5-10; John 5:39; 17:17; 8:32; 7:52; Acts 17:11; 1 Cor 2:10; 2Tim 2:15; 1 Peter 1:10, 11; 3: 15; etc).

5. Ethnographic design
6. Grounded theory design
7. Mixed-methods design
8. Longitudinal design
9. Cross-sectional design

A well-crafted research design helps ensure:

1. Quality and rigor
2. Valid and reliable findings
3. Effective use of resources
4. Answers to research questions
5. Contributions to the field of study

Key components of research design include:

1. **Research Objectives and Questions:** Specifies the purpose and what the study aims to address.
2. **Types of Research:** Identifies the nature of the research—exploratory, descriptive, explanatory, or experimental—guiding the choice of data collection methods.
3. **Data Sources:** Outlines whether data comes from primary sources (like surveys and interviews) or secondary sources (existing data).
4. **Sampling Method:** Details on how participants or data points will be selected.
5. **Data Collection Techniques:** Specifies methods for gathering data (e.g., observations, experiments).
6. **Variables and Measurements:** Defines the variables involved and how they will be measured.
7. **Data Analysis Plan:** Outlines how data will be analysed.
8. **Ethics and Limitations:** Considers ethical implications and potential study limitations

Biblical Research Design

Biblical research design refers to the systematic planning and structuring of research projects that explore biblical texts, themes, and concepts. Biblical research types help scholars and students understand the Bible more deeply and comprehensively. It involves:

1. Defining research questions and objectives
2. Selecting appropriate research methods (qualitative, quantitative, or mixed)
3. Identifying relevant biblical texts and data
4. Developing a sampling strategy (if applicable)
5. Choosing data analysis techniques
6. Ensuring methodological integrity and rigor
7. Considering ethical implications

A well-designed biblical research project should include:

1. Clearly articulate research questions and objectives
2. Employ suitable research methods and tools
3. Demonstrate a thorough understanding of biblical context and hermeneutics
4. Ensure accuracy, reliability, and validity in data collection and analysis
5. Interpret findings in light of biblical theology and scholarship
6. Contribute meaningfully to the field of biblical learning or studies

Research designs in biblical research may include:

1. Exegetical design (in-depth analysis of a specific text)
2. Comparative design (comparing different texts or themes)
3. Correlational design (examining relationships between variables)
4. Experimental design (testing the impact of a biblical intervention)
5. Survey design (collecting data through questionnaires or interviews)
6. Ethnographic design (studying the cultural context of biblical interpretation)
7. Historical design (analysing the historical context and development of biblical texts)

Etc.

Research Type and Design

Research type categorizes the kind of research being conducted based on the overall approach and purpose of the study. Common research types are listed and some of them are explained below. Research design and research type are related but they are distinct concepts in the research process. Research type refers to the overall approach or methodology used to conduct the research (e.g., qualitative, quantitative, mixed-methods). It determines the overall direction and scope of the study. For examples, experimental, survey, case study, ethnography, etc. On the other hands, research Design specifies the detailed plan and structure of the study within the chosen research type; it outlines the methods and procedures for data collection, analysis, and interpretation; and addresses the research questions, sampling, data collection tools, and analysis techniques. In summary, research type provides the broad framework (qualitative, quantitative, etc.) while research design provides the detailed plan within that framework (case study, experimental, etc.). In essence, both are essential components of a research project, working together to ensure a well-planned and rigorous study.

Furthermore, Research design can sometimes function as research type, and the terms are often used interchangeably. However, there is a subtle distinction. Research Type typically refers to the broad category or approach of research, such as: Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed-methods, Exegetical, Historical, Theological, etc. while Research Design typically refers to the specific plan or structure of the study, such as: Case study, Comparative, Correlational, Experimental, Survey, etc. In some cases, a research design can be so closely associated with a particular research type that the terms become synonymous. For example: Exegetical research design (which is a type of qualitative research), Historical research design (which is a type of qualitative research), and Experimental research design (which is a type of quantitative research). In these cases, the research design and research type are essentially the same thing. However, it's still important to recognize that research design typically refers to the specific plan or structure, while research type refers to the broader category or approach.

Types of Biblical Research

1. Biblical Historical Research

The Bible contains a large wealth of historical information that can be studied and researched. Although the Bible is a theopneustic book of God, it is grounded in historical accounts. It contains historical documents that include narratives, genealogies, and accounts of various events. Biblical historical research delves into the history, culture, and context of the Bible. This type of research seeks to uncover the historical events, people, and societal norms that are reflected in the biblical texts. Through archaeological findings, ancient manuscripts, and other historical sources, biblical historical research aims to provide a deeper understanding of the world in which the events of the Bible took place. Biblical historical research is an attempt to construct the past objectively and accurately with biblical evidence. It is a critical investigation of biblical events, developments, and experience of the past objectively and accurately.

For example, the historical books of the Old Testament, such as Genesis, Exodus, Joshua, Judges, Samuel, Kings, and Chronicles, which recount the history of the Israelites, their covenant with God, and their experiences. What about the books of Joshua, Judges, 1 & 2 Samuel, 1 & 2 Kings, 1 & 2 Chronicles, Ezra, Nehemiah, and Esther, which provide detailed accounts of the history of the nation of Israel. These books chronicle the conquest of Canaan, the period of the judges, the establishment of the monarchy, the division of the kingdom, the Babylonian exile, and the return from exile. In the New Testament, this includes the Gospel books, such as Matthew, Mark, Luke, and John, which detail the life, ministry, death, and resurrection of Jesus Christ, along with the Acts of the Apostles, which chronicles the early church's history.

In biblical historical research, scholars often cross-reference biblical accounts with archaeological findings and historical records to better understand the context and accuracy of the events described. However, the Bible is primarily understood as a spiritual guide and theological text rather than a history book in the modern sense. For detailed historical research, a research is expected to study following biblical historical accounts alongside archaeological findings and historical context provided within the Scriptures.

Key biblical historical aspects include:

1. *Creation and Early Humanity*: Found in Genesis, detailing the creation of the world and early figures like Adam, Eve, Noah, and the Tower of Babel.
2. *Patriarchs*: Stories of Abraham, Isaac, Jacob, and Joseph (Genesis 12-50) describe the origins of the Israelite people.
3. *Exodus*: The liberation of the Israelites from Egypt, led by Moses, as narrated in Exodus.
4. *Kings and Prophets*: The establishment of Israel's monarchy, including Saul, David, and Solomon (1 Samuel, 2 Samuel, 1 Kings), and the messages from prophets like Isaiah and Jeremiah.
5. *Exile and Return*: The Babylonian exile and the subsequent return to Jerusalem, as chronicled in books like Ezra and Nehemiah.
6. *Life of Jesus*: The Gospels (Matthew, Mark, Luke, John) provide a historical account of Jesus' life, teachings, death, and resurrection.
7. *Early Church*: The Acts of the Apostles chronicles the spread of Christianity after Jesus' ascension.

In exploring biblical historical research, it is important to consider the methods and approaches used by scholars in this field. One key aspect of biblical historical research is the use of archaeology to unearth physical evidence that may support or shed light on biblical accounts. For example, excavations in Israel have uncovered artefacts and structures that provide insights into daily life during biblical times. These findings can help corroborate or challenge certain aspects of biblical narratives, offering a more nuanced understanding of the historical context. Biblical historical research involves studying the historical context and accuracy of the Bible. Here are some steps and considerations for conducting biblical historical research:

1. Understand the historical context: Study the time period, culture, and geography of the biblical account.
2. Consult multiple sources: Use various historical sources, including archaeological findings, ancient texts, and non-biblical records.
3. Analyze biblical texts: Examine the language, genre, and literary style of the biblical text.
4. Evaluate evidence: Assess the strength and reliability of historical evidence.
5. Consider multiple perspectives: Look at different interpretations and scholarly debates on the subject of discussion.
6. Be aware of biases: Recognize your own biases and try to approach the research objectively.

Some recommended resources for biblical historical research include:

- Commentaries: Scholarly commentaries on biblical books.
- Historical atlases: Maps and geographical resources.
- Archaeological reports: Excavation findings and artifact analysis.
- Ancient texts: Non-biblical texts from the same time period.
- Scholarly journals: Peer-reviewed articles and research papers.

Another important aspect of biblical historical research is the study of ancient texts and manuscripts. Scholars analyse not only the content of these texts but also their language, writing style, and cultural references to gain a better understanding of the societies in which they were produced. By comparing different versions of biblical texts and examining related literature from the same time period, researchers can piece together a more comprehensive picture of the historical background against which these texts were written.

Furthermore, biblical historical research often involves exploring the socio-political dynamics of ancient civilizations. This includes studying rulers, laws, customs, and religious practices as they are depicted in both biblical and non-biblical sources. By contextualizing these elements within their respective historical periods, scholars can paint a more detailed portrait of the environments in which key events from the Bible unfolded.

In conclusion, biblical historical research is a multifaceted endeavor that employs various tools and disciplines to illuminate the historical background of the Bible. Through archaeology, textual analysis, and cultural exploration, scholars seek to enrich our understanding of ancient societies and their relevance to biblical narratives. This field not only provides valuable insights into history but also fosters a deeper appreciation for the complexities underlying one of humanity's most influential literary works.

Examples of biblical historical research topics:

Old Testament

1. The historicity of the Exodus
2. The conquest of Canaan: History or myth?
3. The United Monarchy: David and Solomon's reigns
4. The divide of the kingdoms: Israel and Judah
5. The Babylonian exile: Causes and consequences
6. The Persian period: Return from exile and reconstruction

New Testament

1. The historical Jesus: Life, teachings, and death
2. The apostolic era: Early Christianity's spread
3. The life and missionary journeys of Paul
4. The historical context of the Gospels
5. The early Christian communities: Structure and practices
6. The relationship between Christianity and Judaism
7. The persecution of early Christians: Historical evidence
8. The development of the New Testament canon

2. Biblical Archaeology Research

Biblical Archaeological Research is the scientific investigation of the material remains of ancient cultures mentioned in the Bible to establish the truth of God's word. It is the exploration of the material remains of ancient cultures and history. Biblical Archaeological Research enriches our understanding of the biblical world and its historical context. Examples of Biblical Archaeological Research include: (1.) The discovery of the Hittite Empire (1906); (2.) The excavation of Jericho (1930s); (3.) The Dead Sea Scrolls (1947); (4.) The Tel Dan Inscription (1993): Verified the existence of the House of David a key biblical dynasty, etc. Biblical Archaeological Research may cover some areas such as:

1. Excavation: Careful uncovering of artefacts and sites.
2. Surveying: Systematic exploration of regions and sites.
3. Epigraphy: Study of ancient inscriptions.

4. Numismatics: Analysis of coins.

5. Ceramics and material culture: Examination of pottery, tools, and other artefacts.

This type of biblical research seeks to:

1. Verify historical accuracy: Confirm or challenge the biblical account through archaeological findings.

2. Illuminate cultural context: Understand the daily life, practices, and beliefs of ancient civilizations.

3. Reconstruct historical events: Piece together the sequence of events and their significance.

3. Biblical Descriptive Research

Generally, descriptive research aims to provide a comprehensive overview of a subject or phenomenon by detailing "what" exists rather than "why" it exists. It often uses surveys and observational techniques. It can provide insight into population characteristics at a specific point in time. Descriptive research is also called normative research⁶

The Purpose of biblical descriptive research approach is to:

- Identify problems or justify current conditions and practices from a biblical frame of reference.
- Collect detailed factual information that describes existing phenomenon in the Bible.
- Determine with biblical judgement what others are doing in favour or against the word of God.
- To compare and evaluate current conditions and practices.

For example, the Bible documents a descriptive approach to inquiry when Moses sent representatives of the 12 tribes to search the land of Canaan, he directed them to spy the land⁷:

⁶ Omoyola, A.K. "Need for research and basic research designs in education and the social science" in Olu-Aderounmu, W. O and Bandele, S. O(eds.) *Methods of educational research, A book of reading*. Vol.1, 1990.p. 12

⁷ John Wesley Taylor V. "A Biblical Perspective for Research". *Journal of Adventist Education*, 2019.

¹⁷ And Moses sent them to spy out the land of Canaan, and said unto them, Get you up this way southward, and go up into the mountain: ¹⁸ And see the land, what it is; and the people that dwelleth therein, whether they be strong or weak, few or many; ¹⁹ And what the land is that they dwell in, whether it be good or bad; and what cities they be that they dwell in, whether in tents, or in strong holds; ²⁰ And what the land is, whether it be fat or lean, whether there be wood therein, or not. And be ye of good courage, and bring of the fruit of the land. Now the time was the time of the firstripe grapes (Number 13:17-20)⁸

First thing Moses (the research supervisor) did was to delimit and define the purpose of the study when he told the people (the spies, the researchers) to go up to South region (Negeb), and then go up into the hill to see what the land is like and the people who live in it (Numbers 13:17, 18).

Then Moses describes the characteristics of the inhabitants, towns, land, and vegetation, which were the facets or variables of the study, when instructed these individual researchers to find out “whether the people who live there are strong or weak, few or many. What kind of land do they live in? Is it good or bad? What kind of towns do they live in? Are they unwalled or fortified? How is the soil? Is it fertile or poor? Are there trees in it or not?” (Numbers 13:18-20)⁹.

Moses concluded his assignment to the spies by requesting those carrying out the study (the researchers) to gather a sample: “Do your best to bring back some of the fruit of the land” (vs. 20). In all, Moses, the research supervisor, gave a well-designed approach to descriptive research in this passage of the Scripture.

Having analysed and interpreted their data, the 12 researchers submitted their research findings and recommendations for assessment. Unfortunately, there were divergent reports, leading to divergent conclusions, which depended on the researchers’ assumptions, worldviews, and faith in God (vs. 26-33). In biblical research, presuppositions are based on God’s promises and our faith in Him. Any assumptions or presuppositions that are not rooted in the word of God are not valid and should be reject. Any biblical research work based on human assumptions should be reject. Hence, biblical research is different from secular research. The former is rooted in the word of God while the latter is rooted in the word of man. In secular or scientific research, majority is always right but not so in biblical research.

4. Biblical Quasi-Experimental Research

Quasi-experimental research is a research design that involves studying the effects of an intervention or treatment without randomly assigning participants to groups. Unlike true experiments, quasi-experiments do not manipulate variables or control for extraneous factors. Instead, they exploit natural or existing variations in the environment to examine relationships and outcomes. Similarly, Biblical quasi-experimental research involves applying quasi-experimental designs to study the effects of divine interventions, events, or teachings in the Bible through natural objects, such as wind, fire, water, animal, etc. There are quantum examples of quasi-experimental research design in the Bible. A few of these examples are mentioned here.

⁸ All biblical quotations in this work are from the King James Version except otherwise indicated.

⁹ Ibid.

Examples of quasi-experimental designs include:

1. Natural/Divine intervention experiments (e.g., studying the effects of a natural disaster; the book of Exodus speaks volume of a divine intervention experiment where God frees the Israelites from slavery, demonstrating His power and care (Exodus 1-18). Also, in the book of Acts of Apostles in the New Testament, the Early Church experiences the outpouring of God's power, especially in Acts 2. This is a divine intervention experiment where the Holy Spirit empowers believers, illustrating the power of faith through use of natural symbols, such as wind, fire to represent God's presence.
2. Interrupted time-series designs (e.g., analysing data before and after a policy change). The Divided Kingdom is an interrupted time-series design where the Israelites are divided into two kingdoms, showing the effects of disobedience (1 Kings 12-2 Kings 25).
3. Comparative case studies (e.g., comparing outcomes between two similar groups). The Conquest of Canaan is a biblical example of comparative case study where God gives the Israelites victory over the Canaanites, illustrating the consequences of obedience (Joshua 1-12). Similarly, in the New Testament, The Ministry of Jesus in the gospel books of Matthew, Mark, Luke, and John encapsulates a comparative case study where Jesus teaches, heals, and saves, demonstrating God's love.
4. Regression discontinuity designs (e.g., examining the impact of a threshold or cut-off). The Babylonian Exile is regression discontinuity design where God disciplines His people through exile, leading to repentance (2 Kings 25, Jeremiah 52)

Daniel's Vegetarian Diet Example: A typical Quasi-Experimental Research Design

Daniel chapter one is a great example of a quasi-experimental design in the Bible where Daniel and his other three friends (Hananiah, Mishael, and Azariah) ate only vegetables and water, showing the effects of a healthy diet. In this chapter, King Nebuchadnezzar orders that the young men in his court, including Daniel and his friends, be trained in the Babylonian ways and fed the king's food and wine for three years (Daniel 1:5). However, Daniel and his friends requested an exception, asking to be allowed to eat only vegetables and water for 10 days (Daniel 1:12). Indeed, the Book of Daniel presents what may be known as one of the earliest examples of a quasi-experimental approach to research, a single-factor post-test design¹⁰. First of all, when confronted with Nebuchadnezzar's dietary regime, Daniel and his other three Hebrew fellow students at the Royal University of Babylon proposed a comparative study. First, they set out the research protocol¹¹:

Please test your servants for ten days: Give us nothing but vegetables to eat and water to drink. Then compare our appearance with that of the young men who eat the royal food, and treat your servants in accordance with what you see (NIV Daniel 1:12, 13).

This scenario can be seen as a quasi-experiment, where:

- **The independent variable** is the diet with two levels (king's food and wine vs. vegetables and water)

¹⁰Ibd. John Wesley Taylor V. "A Biblical Perspective for Research". *Journal of Adventist Education*, 2019.

¹¹ Ibid.

- **The dependent variable** is the outcome (health, appearance, and wisdom)
- **The control group** is the young men who ate the king's food and wine
- **The experimental group/ treatment group** is Daniel and his friends who ate only vegetables and water.

Indeed, the result of this "experiment" is that Daniel and his friends appear healthier and wiser than the others, and they are allowed to continue their vegetarian diet (Daniel 1:15-16). The study included a longitudinal component. Three years later, when the students rendered their comprehensive exam, after the post-test, Daniel and his three friends were found to be 10 times better than the magicians and astrologers, the other young student in the class who ate the king's meal (Daniel 1:20), a group, incidentally, that included their instructors¹². This passage illustrates a quasi-experimental design, where a natural intervention (the diet) is observed and compared to a control group, demonstrating the effects of the intervention (Daniel 1:1-21). This is, indeed, beyond natural intervention. it was a divine intervention employing natural object.

It should be noted that these examples illustrate how quasi-experimental designs can be applied to biblical education, exploring the effects of divine interventions and human actions without manipulating variables. Quasi-experimental research provides valuable insights into causal relationships and can inform decision-making, even without the control of a true experiment.

The following are the fundamental characteristics of quasi-experimental research:

1. No random assignment to groups
2. No manipulation of variables
3. It uses existing or natural or divine variations
4. It compares groups or outcomes
5. Infers causality based on observed relationships

Quasi-experiments are often used in situations where:

1. Random assignment is not feasible
2. Manipulating variables is unethical or impractical
3. Studying rare or unique events
4. Examining longitudinal or historical data

5. The Biblical Qualitative Approach

Biblical qualitative research is an approach to biblical research that combines the principles of qualitative research with biblical theology and methods. It seeks to understand and interpret biblical texts, concepts, and phenomena through in-depth, contextual, and nuanced analysis. Data is collected using surveys, experiments, and observational methods, often presented in the form of charts and graphs.

¹² Ibid.

Qualitative research is a research methodology that focuses on gathering and analysing non-numerical data to gain insights and understanding of a particular phenomenon, context, or population. It involves collecting and interpreting data through methods such as:

1. Interviews (in-depth, semi-structured, or focus groups)
2. Observations (participant or non-participant)
3. Focus groups
4. Content analysis (of texts, images, or videos)
5. Case studies
6. Ethnography
7. Grounded theory
8. Phenomenology
9. Discourse analysis

The Aims of Qualitative Research

1. Explore and understand the meaning and interpretation of experiences, behaviours, or phenomena
2. Identify patterns, themes, and relationships
3. Develop theories or concepts
4. Provide rich, detailed, and contextualized insights

Characteristics of Qualitative Research:

1. Subjective and interpretive
2. Focus on meaning and context
3. Small sample sizes
4. Data collection and analysis are often simultaneous
5. Flexibility and adaptability in the research design
6. Emphasis on the researcher's role and reflexivity

Qualitative research is commonly used in social sciences, education, healthcare, marketing, and anthropology to study complex issues, gain nuanced insights, and develop context-specific solutions.

Biblical qualitative research is an approach to research that combines the principles of qualitative research with biblical theology and methods. It seeks to understand and interpret biblical texts, concepts, and phenomena through in-depth, contextual, and nuanced analysis.

Characteristics of Biblical Qualitative Research:

1. It is biblically focused. It examines the biblical texts, themes, and concepts in their original context.
2. It integrates biblical theology and hermeneutics into the research process.
3. It employs qualitative research methods (e.g., content analysis, case studies, ethnography) to analyse biblical data.
4. It brings into fore the Contextual understanding. In other words, it seeks to understand the historical, cultural, and literary context of biblical texts.
5. It gives interpretive approach to biblical texts. That is, it recognises the importance of interpretation and seeks to uncover the meaning of biblical texts through careful analysis.
6. It encourages researchers to reflect on their own biases, assumptions, and theological perspectives.
7. It helps to gain a deeper understanding of biblical texts and their relevance to contemporary contexts.

Biblical qualitative research can be applied to various areas, such as:

1. Biblical Christian education: Exploring the teaching and learning of biblical education in various contexts of human endeavours.
2. Biblical studies: In-depth analysis of biblical texts, genres, and themes.
3. Theological education: Exploring the teaching and learning of theology in various contexts.
4. Biblical counselling: Examining the application of biblical principles in counselling and pastoral care.
5. Christian ministry: Understanding the practices and experiences of biblical Christian ministry and mission.

In qualitative biblical approach, the Bible presents instances of naturalistic inquiry. For example, Luke became a participant observer in Paul's missionary journeys, reporting events that he experienced. Notice the transition to the first person beginning in Troas until Philippi, and then several years later, from Philippi onward to Rome (see Acts 16:10-40; Acts 20:6 onward).¹³

Similarly, cases of direct observation may be found in Peter and John's examination of the tomb where Jesus had been buried (John 20:1-8); Gideon's observation of the wet and dry fleece (Judges 6:36-40); and Nehemiah's nocturnal inspection of the ruins of Jerusalem, through which he corroborated interview data (Nehemiah 1:2, 3; 2:11-17). In His day, Jesus remarked that persons would make predictions based on qualitative observations of natural phenomena but were not applying a similar process to the "signs of the times" (Matthew 16:2-4)¹⁴. According to John Wesley Taylor, another example can be found in Jesus' instruction to the two disciples of John the Baptist, who came to Him to ask Him they had brought from John the Baptist, "Are you the one who is to come, or should we expect someone else?" After they stood by for a time, waiting for an answer, Jesus told them, "Go back and report to John what you have seen and heard: The blind receive sight, the lame walk, those who have leprosy are cleansed, the deaf hear, the dead are raised, and the good news is proclaimed to the poor" (Luke 7:18-22)¹⁵.

According to the Bible, the Bereans triangulated what they heard with document analysis (Acts 17:11). This crosscheck of data sources fits well with the biblical injunction that a matter is established with evidence from two or three witnesses (Deuteronomy 17:6; 19:15; Matthew 18:16; 2 Corinthians 13:1; 1 Timothy 5:19; Hebrews 10:28). Even the witness of the apostles was based on the triangulation of what they had seen and what they had heard (Acts 4:20)¹⁶. Thus, biblical research is evidence based.

6. Biblical Quantitative Research

Quantitative research is a research methodology that focuses on collecting and analysing numerical data to understand a phenomenon or problem. It has the following vital Characteristics:

1. Numerical data collection
2. Statistical analysis
3. Objective measurement
4. Large sample sizes
5. Hypothesis testing

¹³ John Wesley Taylor V. "A Biblical Perspective for Research". *Journal of Adventist Education*, 2019.

¹⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Ibid.

6. Predictive modeling

7. Generalizability

Methods:

1. Surveys

2. Experiments

3. Quasi-experiments

4. Correlational studies

5. Longitudinal studies

6. Content analysis (quantitative)

7. Statistical modelling

Data Collection Tools are;

1. Questionnaires

2. Interviews (structured)

3. Observational studies

4. Secondary data analysis

5. Online polls

Data Analysis Techniques are:

1. Descriptive statistics

2. Inferential statistics

3. Regression analysis

4. Factor analysis

5. Cluster analysis

6. Time-series analysis

It has the following Advantages:

1. Objectivity
2. Reliability
3. Generalizability
4. Precision
5. Efficiency

Limitations to Quantitative research are:

1. Complexity
2. Assumption-dependent
3. Contextual limitations
4. Difficulty in capturing nuances
5. Dependence on data quality

Quantitative Research approach can be used in various Fields, such as:

1. Social sciences
2. Business and economics
3. Healthcare and medicine
4. Education
5. Psychology
6. Engineering
7. Environmental science
8. Theology and Biblical education

Examples:

1. Analysing customer satisfaction ratings
2. Measuring the effect of a new teaching method
3. Studying the relationship between exercise and weight loss
4. Evaluating the impact of a marketing campaign
5. Investigating the correlation between IQ and academic achievement

Similarly, biblical quantitative research combines quantitative research methods with biblical studies or education to analyse and interpret biblical data. It employs numerical methods to:

1. Examine biblical texts and themes
2. Identify patterns and trends
3. Test hypotheses
4. Measure correlations
5. Predict outcomes

Characteristics:

1. Uses quantitative methods (e.g., statistics, surveys)
2. Focuses on biblical texts, themes, and concepts
3. Employs objective measurement and analysis
4. Seeks to generalize findings to broader biblical contexts
5. Integrates biblical theology and hermeneutics

Methods:

1. Textual analysis (e.g., word frequency, sentiment analysis)
2. Survey research (e.g., biblical knowledge, attitudes)
3. Correlational studies (e.g., biblical values and behaviour)

4. Experimental designs (e.g., testing biblical interventions)
5. Statistical modelling (e.g., predicting biblical outcomes)

Tools:

1. Biblical software (e.g., Logos, Accordance)
2. Statistical software (e.g., SPSS, R)
3. Survey instruments (e.g., questionnaires, scales)
4. Data visualization tools (e.g., charts, graphs)

It can be applied to many areas of biblical education, such as:

1. Biblical Christian education
2. Christian education
3. Biblical studies
4. Theological education
5. Christian ministry
6. Biblical counselling
7. Missions and evangelism

Examples:

1. Analysing the frequency of biblical themes across genres
2. Measuring the relationship between biblical knowledge and spiritual growth
3. Evaluating the effectiveness of biblical-based interventions
4. Identifying patterns in biblical leadership styles
5. Investigating the correlation between biblical values and social justice

Etc.

Biblical quantitative research provides insights into biblical texts and their application, informing theology, education, ministry, and practice.

Biblical quantitative research and biblical quantitative research provide valuable insights through non-numerical and numerical data analysis, enabling researchers to identify patterns, trends, and correlations, and make informed decisions. These two approaches can be combined by a researcher to leverage the strengths of both. It allows for comprehensive investigation by offering both numerical data and rich descriptive insights. However, we need to keep in mind that both biblical research approaches are emerging fields, and their methodologies and applications continue to evolve.

7. Biblical-Biographical Research:

Biblical Biographical Research can be referred to as biographical or character study. It is a method of studying the Bible by examining the lives of its characters. This type of biblical research relates to the account of a biblical figure, his or her life, roles, ministry (office), how God used him or her, etc. This also relates to historical research but only focuses on the account of a person's life in the Bible. For example, the Life and Death of Jesus; the Birth of Jesus; the Theology and Life of Paul; and so on. Historical research and biographical research can be used together in biblical research. This biblical research approach provides deep insights into the spiritual lessons derived from the stories of biblical figures, allowing readers to apply these lessons to their own lives.

The intention of Biblical Biographical Research is to uncover spiritual truths that can inform and transform the lives of contemporary believers. As stated in various sources, life stories captured in the Bible provide examples of both successes and failures, that is, we can learn something of their problems and victories, from which readers can learn valuable lessons¹⁷. For example, we can select a Bible character, say Peter, and research all the verses about that person in order to study his life and characteristics better. Then, we make notes on his attitudes, strengths, and weaknesses. After that, we can apply what we have learned to our own personal life¹⁸. No doubt, The Bible serves as a single largest collections of biographies, wherein characters illustrate different aspects of faith and human experience. By studying these figures, we engage in a search for truth – not only to learn *what* they did but also *why* they acted as they did and how their experiences relate to our own lives today¹⁹

¹⁷ SDA Sabbath School Lessons March 9, 1996. <https://ssnet.org/qrtrly/eng/96a/96a10.html>

¹⁸ Warren, Rick. "The Biographical Method". <http://www.olemissxa.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/The-Biographical-Method.pdf>.

¹⁹ Ellison, Les. "Biblical Biographies - Bible lives and yours in God's great continuing story". <https://www.eden.co.uk/blog/biblical-biographies---bible-lives-and-yours-in-gods-great-continuing-story-p1148>

Steps in Conducting a Biographical Research

1. *Selecting a Character:* Choose a biblical character whose life intrigues you. For beginners, it is better and recommended to start with a person on whom you can do a simple study to avoid being overwhelmed by the depth of material available on characters like Moses, Abraham or Jesus. One can begin with some minor but important people such as Andrew, Barnabas, or Mary of Bethany²⁰.
2. *Gathering Information:* Utilize tools such as a concordance or online Bible resources to compile references related to the selected character. Make a list of all pertinent scriptures that mention or relate to that character²¹
3. *Analyzing the Data:* Carefully read through the collected passages. Note the character's traits, experiences, major life events, and their relationship with God. Questions to consider include their strengths, weaknesses, and how they addressed challenges²².
4. *Character Evaluation:* Identify both positive and negative traits exhibited by the character. Observe how these traits influenced their decisions and spiritual growth. Ask questions about their impact on their families and communities, as well as their legacy²³
5. *Making Personal Applications:* Reflect on the life lessons learned from the character's experiences. How can you apply these lessons to your personal faith journey? Identify specific areas in your life that may benefit from this newfound understanding²⁴
6. *Sharing Insights:* Communicate what you've learned with others, whether in a group study or personal conversation. This not only reinforces your learning but also helps others in their faith journeys²⁵

7. BIBLICAL CASUAL-COMPARATIVE RESEARCH

Causal-comparative research investigates the cause and effect relationship between two variables, such as independent and dependent variables, without manipulating those variables by observing

²⁰ Op.cit. Warren, Rick.

²¹ Warren, Rick. See also Giessl, Janet. "How to Do a Biographical Bible Study", 2022. <https://wisdomfromheaven.net/how-to-do-a-biographical-bible-study/>

²² Op.cit. Ellison, Les

²³ See Tammie. "How to Do a Biographical Bible Study | Learning From Others' Lives". <https://www.lifeloveandjesus.com/biographical-bible-study/>

²⁴ Op.cit. Giessl, Janet, 2022

²⁵ Op.cit. Tammie

consequences and then working back from these consequences through available data for possible causal factors²⁶. Thus, Biblical casual-comparative research refers to a research methodology that seeks to understand the cause and effect between two variables, compare phenomena, principles, or practices as depicted within the armpit of biblical accounts and their implications for contemporary issues and biblical Christians. We can cite a few biblical examples here: (1.) Why Adam and his wife, Eve decided to eat the forbidden fruit in Genesis 3? (2.) What are the factors that caused Cain to kill his brother, Abel in Genesis 4? (3) Why God rejected King Saul as king over Israel in 1Samuel 15? (4) We can also look at how Moses and David responded to leadership challenges and compare their responses to the leadership styles evident in modern organizational settings based on biblical principles. What led to three acts of denial of Jesus by the Apostle Peter as described in all four Gospels of the New Testament? All these examples are good Biblical Casual-Comparative research topics. The researcher who employs this type of biblical research will first identify the causes of their actions and look at the consequences (the effects).

Steps in Biblical Casual-Comparative Research

1. Define the problem e.g. Adam and Eve ate the forbidden fruit; Cain killed his brother Abel; God rejected King Saul; etc.
2. State the hypotheses or leading questions.
3. List the assumptions upon which the hypotheses or questions will be based
4. Design the approach by selecting the construction technique and biblical frame of reference for data collection.
5. Validate data collection technique with biblical frame of reference.
6. Analyse, describe and interpret the findings in lucid or clear and precise term.
7. Report your finding and show its implication to support your argument, case or position.

Other Types of Biblical Research

1. Exegetical Research: Detailed analysis, explanation or interpretation of a specific biblical passage or verse.
2. Literary Research: Studies the literary structure, genre, and themes of a biblical text.
4. Theological Research: Explores the theological themes and concepts within a biblical text.
5. Hermeneutical Research: Focuses on the interpretation and understanding of biblical texts.
6. Sociological Research: Examines the social context and implications of biblical texts.
7. Redactional Research: Analyses the editorial process and changes made to biblical texts, such as language, etc.
8. Intertextuality Research: Explores relationships and connections between different biblical texts.

²⁶ Omoyola, A.K. "Need for research and basic research designs in education and social sciences" in Olu-Aderounmu, W.O and Bandele, S.O (eds.). *Methods of educational research: A book of readings*, (Kola Okanlawon Publishers Ltd, 1990) pp. 8-17.

9. Biblical Criticism Research: Examines the authenticity, authorship, and historical accuracy of biblical texts.
10. Biblical Linguistics Research: Studies the languages and linguistic features of biblical texts.
11. Biblical Historical-Critical Research: Examination of a biblical text's historical context, authorship, and redaction history to understand its original meaning.
12. Biblical Biographical Research: This can be called biographical or character study. It is a method of studying the Bible by examining the lives of its characters. This type of biblical research relates to the account of a biblical figure, his or her life, roles, ministry (office), how God used him or her, etc.
13. Apocalyptic research: Studies the apocalyptic genre and themes in the Bible.
14. Prophetic research: Examines the prophetic literature and themes in the Bible.
15. New Testament research: Focuses on the study of the New Testament texts, themes, and contexts.
16. Old Testament research: Focuses on the study of the Old Testament texts, themes, and contexts.
17. Experimental research: Tests the impact of biblical interventions, such as the effect of prayer or Bible study on spiritual growth.
18. Survey research: Collects data through questionnaires or interviews to understand biblical knowledge, attitudes, or practices.
19. Ethnographic research: Studies the cultural context and practices of biblical interpretation in different communities.
20. Correlational research: Examines relationships between biblical variables, such as the connection between faith and practice.
21. Pneumatic Research: Unlike secular research, biblical research is Spirit-led inquiry. Only the spiritual man can understand the things of the spirit because they are spiritually coded and interpreted (2Cor 2: 1-16). In this type of research, the researcher engages himself or herself in what this author calls, *spiritual-intellectual epistemology*.
22. Action Research: This is a reflective process where practitioners seek to improve their actions through systematic inquiry, typically within a specific context like education or organizational change.
23. Solus Primus Scriptura Research (SPSR): Solus Primus *Scriptura Research* (bibliosearch) is a coined term used by Dele Alaba Ilesanmi, to promote biblically based research work. Solus primus *scriptura search* (bibliosearch) is a type of research that relies primarily only on first-hand evidence from the impeccable source of God's work, the Bible, as accurate, reliable, and inerrant source. All the evidence from this source is considered accurate, reliable, and inerrant because it is directly from the author's mouth (God).

It should be noted that these types of biblical research often overlap or are used in combination to provide a comprehensive understanding of the Bible.

Conclusion

The study has been able to discuss research and biblical research, types of biblical designs and biblical research types embellished with copious biblical examples as guide and framework to biblical research methodology. The discussion here is not exhaustive. It is believed, therefore, that this attempt will give birth to fresh ideas or thoughts in the field of biblical research to push back the frontiers of human ignorance.

The Author

Pastor Dele Alaba Ilesanmi (B.Ed., PGDE, PGDTh., PDGM., M.A., Ph.D, ThD.) is a theoretical and applied biblical Christian educator who has been a lecturer at the Redeemed Christian Bible College (Satellite Campuses) since 2008 and an Associate Research Professor at Testament Theological Seminary with expertise in Biblical Christian Education and Biblical Research (the fields he is currently pioneering). His academic interest is primarily in the fields of Theoretical and Applied Biblical Christian Education and Research. He has developed some biblical theories and concepts, such as *Theogenesial Theory*, *Pneumagenesial Theory*, *Quantum Theory*, *Theory of Absolute Ownership-Creationism*, *Parabolic Differential Learning Theory*, *Supra-nationalistic Salvation Theory*, *Divino-Experiential Learning Theory*, *Divino-Constructivism*, *Continual Learning Theory*, *Theogogy*, *Pneumagogy*, *Christogogy*, *Bibliogogy*, *Bibliogogics*, *Homeogogy/Filiogogy*, etc. As of 2023, he has over 80 publications to his credit, including nine books and Christian research articles published in different reputable and registered journals and websites. To connect with this astute author: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4874-0759>; pstdeleilesanmi3@gmail.com; +234-08062197040

References

- Ellison, Les. "Biblical biographies - bible lives and yours in God's great continuing story". <https://www.eden.co.uk/blog/biblical-biographies---bible-lives-and-yours-in-gods-great-continuing-story-p1148>
- Giessl, Janet. "How to Do a Biographical Bible Study", 2022. <https://wisdomfromheaven.net/how-to-do-a-biographical-bible-study/>
- Ilesanmi, Dele Alaba. "Biblical research: A theological and epistemological inquiry" in *Mature journal of the institute of Christian theologians, scholars, and professionals*, Vol. 2(2), 2024.
- Ilesanmi, Dele A. "The need for biblical research and publication beyond secularism: Concepts and importance" in *Mature journal of the institute of Christian theologians, scholars, and professionals*, Vol. 2(3), 2024.
- John Wesley Taylor V. "A biblical perspective for research". *Journal of Adventist Education*, 2019.
- Omoyola, A.K. "Need for research and basic research designs in education and social sciences" in Olu-Aderounmu, W.O and Bandele, S.O (eds.). *Methods of educational research: A book of readings*, (Kola Okanlawon Publishers Ltd, 1990) pp. 8-17.
- SDA Sabbath School Lessons March 9, 1996. <https://ssnet.org/qrtrly/eng/96a/96a10.html>
- Tammie. "How to do a biographical bible study | Learning From Others' Lives". <https://www.lifeloveandjesus.com/biographical-bible-study/>
- Warren, Rick. "The biographical method". <http://www.olemissxa.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/The-Biographical-Method.pdf>.